

Machina Emblematica: Multimodal Information Retrieval Prototype for CH and DH

Final Report for the project funded via the *HERMES-Innovation Forschungsstudienprogramm für Datenkompetenzen in den Geistes- und Kulturwissenschaften 2025*

Summary of Completed Work: The goal of the project was to implement a simple state of the art Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) system (Li et al. 2024) that makes the digital 1668 edition of Joachim Camerarius' *Symbola et Emblemata* more accessible and explorable (Camerarius 1668). The team published an innovative, user-friendly chatbot prototype that enables users to ask questions about the emblems and search for related multimodal contents in the *Symbola et Emblemata* (Figure 1). Machina Emblematica innovates access and exploration of the Latin/Greek historical contents by providing an assistant that generates user query responses in English based on the most relevant content retrieved via the search backend. The prototype advances existing solutions from projects enhancing accessibility and exploration of historical images and texts e.g. Digital Camerarius¹ (Palladino et al. 2025), Emblematica Online² (Green et al. 2017), and ONiT Explorer³ (Vignoli et al. 2024).

Figure 1: Screenshots of the Machina Emblematica Landing Page

Corpus: Machina Emblematica is built around the [Digital Camerarius](#) transcription of the *Symbola et Emblemata*, which was funded by Furman University. The scanned images of the 1668 printed edition of *Symbola et Emblemata* that can be searched with the RAG system are provided by the Münchener Digitale Bibliothek⁴. In total, the corpus consists of 838 pages containing titles, captions, full texts, and 401 emblems. The small image-text pair corpus provided an excellent use case to demonstrate how embedding-based retrieval (Pan et al. 2024) can be used for retrieving specific contents and intermedial relations in digitized historical sources.

Multimodal Search Backend: This component was developed in context of the Digital Camerarius project funded by Furman University (Palladino et al. 2025). The goal was to enable multimodal embedding-based retrieval of images and full texts combined with lexical search. The advantage of this method is that content retrieval is not restricted to the metadata of images and

¹ <https://github.com/Furman-Editions-In-Progress/camerarius>

² <http://emblematica.library.illinois.edu/>

³ <https://labs.onb.ac.at/en/tool/onit-explorer/>

⁴ <https://www.digitale-sammlungen.de/en/details/bsb10575861>

full text search. Instead, the image and text-chunk vectors are included in the search making specific topics or elements that are not explicitly tagged in the metadata retrievable as well. In a first step, the cleaned texts and images were extracted and vectorized with two distinct models and added to two separate Marqo vector indices⁵. The images were vectorized with an open-CLIP model⁶ and the chunked full texts with the Flax Sentence Embeddings v4 model⁷. The search backend is set up to retrieve the five most similar text pages and images from the corpus based on the user query.

RAG System: The main component developed in context of the HERMES funding consists of a web-based frontend and a RAG system that generates answers to user queries. We opted for a Qwen2.5 model⁸, a state of the art Vision-Language (VL) model that is able to process both visual and textual information. The chatbot is configured to answer the user query based on the multimodal sources retrieved by the search backend. Users can enter a question via the chatbot frontend, e.g. “What moral lessons can we learn from the crocodile?” (Figure 2). In a first step, the entered user query is contextualised and passed to the retriever. In a second step, the retrieval results are normalized and merged into a natural language context string and an image link array that are passed to the VL-model. Subsequently, the model generates an answer to the user question based on the most relevant data provided by the retriever. In addition to summarizing the content found in English language, the frontend displays previews and direct links to the original pages of the digital resources retrieved by the search backend. The method provides a transparent EU AI-Act conform solution for multimodal information retrieval of digitized historical sources.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the Machina Camerarius Chatbot

Limitations and Future Work: It is important to note that the present implementation of the Machina Emblematica is an early prototype set up to provide entertaining and eased access to the Latin texts and emblematic contents. The tool is still under development. While the Machina can in principle be used to help retrieving relevant material for answering research questions, we did not test the system’s capabilities for this application context. As Finn and Khosrowi point out,

⁵ <https://www.marqo.ai/>

⁶ Open-CLIP ViT-B-32 pre-trained on the LAION-2B English subset of LAION-5B: <https://huggingface.co/laion/CLIP-ViT-B-32-laion2B-s34B-b79K>

⁷ https://huggingface.co/flax-sentence-embeddings/all_datasets_v4_mpnet-base

⁸ <https://huggingface.co/Qwen/Qwen2.5-VL-32B-Instruct>

a clear communication of the capabilities of AI assistants and how they work are essential to avoid misconceptions and to safeguard “rigorous historical practice” (2025). We included a disclaimer in the “About” section of the Machina Emblematica landing page to instruct users to inspect the contents provided by the tool with caution and to consult the original sources where needed. Users are warned that the generated responses may contain errors, gaps, or wrong interpretations. First empirical experiments indicate that the applied Qwen model is capable to correctly understand, translate, and contextualise the Neo-Latin texts and image material in many cases. However, we also observed that the VL-model erroneously interprets contents in some cases (e.g. it misidentifies depicted animals, contents, or scenes). More extensive and methodical testing of the generated answers is required to assess the degrees of factuality and introduced inaccuracies due to model hallucinations in the generated answers. This will be addressed in a future publication. Future research should focus on improving the prototype to provide more accurate and relevant results, e.g. by introducing better reranking of the multimodal retrieval results; experimenting with alternative VL-models for generating the answers; further enriching the metadata and the indexes to improve RAG results; and exploring more advanced system architectures (e.g. by combining RAG with topic modelling, see Keerthana et al. 2025).

Funded Researchers: The basic RAG backend component and frontend were developed by Michela Vignoli and Rainer Simon for the duration of six months in 2025. This project was funded through the BMFTR joint project [HERMES](#).

Links and Resources

The tool was developed with open-source components. The source code is openly available via GitHub. The Machina Emblematica prototype is currently publicly available and can be tested via the link below.

Open Source Repository of the Machina Emblematica Prototype:

<https://github.com/rsimon/machina-emblematica>

Further Documentation of Experiments and Code:

https://github.com/rockmi/machina_emblematica

Current Link to the Machina Emblematica Prototype:

<https://machina.rainersimon.io/>

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